

The Inspiration of Criticizing Obsolete Customs and Affirming Fine Traditional Values in Southern Vietnamese Novels in the Early of the Twentieth Century

Truong Thi Linh ✉

Faculty of Education, Thu Dau Mot University, Viet Nam

Abstract

This article aims to examine the inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs and the inspiration of affirming fine traditional values in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century, thereby clarifying the role of these two forms of inspiration in reflecting and orienting social life. Although issues of morality and customs have been mentioned in several studies, previous works have mainly approached individual aspects separately, without placing these two forms of inspiration in an interactive relationship and without systematically examining them within the scope of Southern Vietnamese novels in the early twentieth-century transitional period. From this gap, the article seeks to identify the manifestations and significance of these two types of inspiration in constructing cultural and social values.

From these analyses, the article affirms that these two forms of inspiration do not exist separately but are interwoven and complementary, carrying both critical and constructive characteristics, thereby contributing to shaping cultural values and social consciousness in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century.

Keywords: *inspiration, critical inspiration, fine traditional values, novel, Southern Vietnamese novel.*

Suggested citation: Linh, T.T. (2026). The Inspiration of Criticizing Obsolete Customs and Affirming Fine Traditional Values in Southern Vietnamese Novels in the Early of the Twentieth Century. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 155-159. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2026.3(3).14

Introduction

Inspiration is often understood as a special psychological state of the author during the creation of a literary work. However, this understanding limits the conceptual scope of the term. Therefore, beyond being a special and momentary psychological state, inspiration is also the author's passion to affirm a belief of a more enduring nature. That is, inspiration is not merely an individual psychological impulse at a given moment but an ideology that the author adheres to throughout the process of artistic creation. In other words, inspiration can be regarded as an "internal logic" that governs the way the author selects topics, themes, characters, and language in creative practice.

In the course of Vietnamese literature in the early twentieth century, particularly in the Southern region, the novel became an important genre reflecting the profound transformations of society during the transitional period. The collision between traditional and modern values gave rise to many issues related to morality, customs, and lifestyle. In this context, in addition to reflecting reality, Southern Vietnamese writers also clearly expressed their attitudes toward obsolete customs, while affirming and promoting the positive values of national tradition.

The inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs and affirming fine traditional values thus became two prominent aspects in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century. On the one

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

hand, these works focus on exposing outdated practices and conservative conceptions that hinder human and social development. On the other hand, writers also aim to honor traditional moral values such as family affection, filial piety, fidelity, and a humane way of life.

Although this issue has been mentioned in several studies, previous research has often approached each aspect separately and has not examined systematically the relationship between critical inspiration and affirmative inspiration within a unified framework. In particular, within the scope of Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century, these two forms of inspiration have not yet been comprehensively and thoroughly studied.

From these issues, the article aims to identify the manifestations of the inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs and the inspiration of affirming fine traditional values in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century, thereby clarifying their roles in reflecting, orienting, and constructing cultural and social values in this particular historical period.

Research Methods

The article employs methods of analysis and synthesis based on the examination of several representative novels of Southern Vietnamese literature in the first half of the twentieth century. The research results show that the inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs is expressed through exposing backward practices and outdated conceptions of marriage, family, and social status, thereby revealing the writers' critical attitude toward factors that hinder human and social development. At the same time, the inspiration of affirming fine traditional values is manifested through the promotion of positive traditional moral values such as family affection, filial piety, fidelity, compassion, and the humane lifestyle of Southern Vietnamese people.

Research Contents

Concept

Thuần phong mỹ tục (custom) refers to “good and wholesome customs” (Nguyễn Kim Thản, Hồ Hải Thụy, & Nguyễn Đức Dương, 2005, p. 1557). This concept includes “thuần phong,” which denotes pure and simple customs, and “mỹ tục,” which refers to good practices. In general terms, *thuần phong mỹ tục* is understood as a concept referring to all customs, practices, morality, and lifestyles—both traditional and modern—that possess positive and healthy characteristics of a community, a nation, a country, or a region, and are widely recognized and followed by people.

Hủ tục (evil customs) are “customs that have become outdated and obsolete” (tratu.soha.vn; Nguyễn Kim Thản, Hồ Hải Thụy, & Nguyễn Đức Dương, 2005, p. 790). In its most common contemporary understanding, *hủ tục* refers to “bad habits and harmful practices that cause society to stagnate and develop slowly” (Phạm Bá Khiêm, 2013). Such customs may have been newly introduced or have emerged in recent times.

The Inspiration for Criticizing Outdated Customs

First, superstitious and irrational customs (such as choosing auspicious dates for building houses, or matching ages for marriage) have caused many families to fall into tragic situations, as seen in *Burning the Almanac* (Bình Trọng, 1931). Another example is the custom of using charms and sorcery in *The Mysterious Scheme of Love* [Tình kế màu nhiệm] (Dương Minh Đạt, 1926). This work tells the story of the love between Trần Bạch Mai and Huỳnh Hà Sang. The two are a well-matched couple, talented and beautiful, and were engaged by their parents. However, during one occasion of going to the theater, Huỳnh Hà Sang was noticed by the actress Đào Mận, who used charms to enchant him, causing him to become infatuated and forget his fiancée.

Second, the custom of traditional marriage, with the notion that “parents decide and children obey,” arranging marriages from a young age, seeking families of similar status, and the principle of “matching social status,” causes human fate to be “threatened and determined by customs, depriving individuals of personal happiness” and “customs are always lurking, ready to bare their fangs and claws against true love and noble marital relationships” (Cao Thị Ngọc Hà, 2016, p. 92). Due to forced marriages arranged by parents, the lives of many young men and women fall into deadlock, misery, and hopelessness.

Hà Hương is forced by her parents-in-law to divorce her husband; Nguyệt Ba is arranged by her parents to marry a man she does not love; Nghĩa Hữu (*Hà Hương phong nguyệt* - Lê Hoàng Mưu). Although Nguyệt Ba has the ability to refuse the marriage, she is a traditional woman, and the notion that “a garment once worn cannot be taken off over the head” is deeply ingrained in her consciousness. For that reason, her life falls into misfortune. Kim Sa is a beautiful and virtuous girl, but because her parents are greedy for wealth, they marry her off to Diệt Tộc. Under his father’s instigation, Diệt Tộc cruelly kills his wife while she is heavily pregnant and close to giving birth (*Mạng nhà nghèo* - Nguyễn Hữu Mịch, 1931).

In another case, cô Đăng (*Dây oan* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1935) loves Mr. Phán Nhãn but is forced by her parents to marry another man. As a traditional woman, she does not dare to oppose this arranged marriage. However, tragedy occurs when she meets her former lover again: she poisons her husband in order to be free to be with her lover, even bearing a child with him rather than with her husband. In another instance, a wife is taken back by her parents because her husband is poor, causing a once happy and harmonious family to suddenly collapse, as in the case of Mỹ Hạnh and Huỳnh Bảo Ngọc (*Ngọc lam diễm* - Phú Đức).

Third, the custom of buying and selling official positions: for the sake of a minor official title, people have to spend enormous sums of money to obtain it. Bá Vạn and Đỗ Thị, for the position of Cai Tổng, eventually lose all their property. The husband, grieving over the loss of wealth, falls ill and dies; the wife and child have to live dependently in the house of the husband’s sister, bà Phủ Khánh Long, in *Money and Wealth* [Tiền bạc bạc tiền] (Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1925). Power causes a once peaceful, prosperous, and happy family to suddenly fall apart. Because positions and material wealth can control people and bring them respect, many are willing to “spend vast sums of money just to obtain a minor official title” (Phú Đức, 1989, p. 32). Those who possess power and wealth can act arrogantly, lecture others, and commit wrongdoings without being punished. Meanwhile, those who are poor in money, material conditions, and power must bow and endure suffering and humiliation.

A submissive figure such as Cai Tuần Bưởi, who is oppressed and insulted by others, still believes that they are doing him a favor and dares not protest due to the mentality that he is poor while they are rich. His gestures and attitude in front of bà Cai Hiếu and the couple cậu Hai Nghĩa reflect the demeanor of someone indebted: bending, bowing, and speaking deferentially. Even when his younger sister is seduced and becomes pregnant, he can only respond gently and inform quietly, not daring to make the matter public, for fear that those with money and power will oppress him further.

Fourth, some customs influenced by the West lead to moral degradation, treating human life as insignificant, and considering dueling with swords or guns as normal in order to assert individual value, as seen in characters such as lawyer Nguyễn Thành Mỹ (*Lửa lòng* [Lửa lòng] - Phú Đức, 1928) and court chief Nguyễn Hào Sanh (*Tình trường huyết lệ* - Phú Đức, 1930). Other examples include the custom of entertaining guests with opium-smoking sessions and courtesans in *Mảnh trăng thu* (Bửu Đình), or indulgent all-night revelries organized through exhibitions in *Lửa lòng* (Phú Đức)...

The Inspiration of Affirming Fine Traditional Values

First, the custom of “valuing righteousness over wealth” and mutual assistance among Southern Vietnamese people, the spirit of “kiến nghĩa bất vi vô đồng dã”: when witnessing wrongdoing, one does not stand by idly; helping others without expecting repayment, such as the family of thầy Liễu treating Thầy Phiền as a member of the family (*Thầy Lazarô Phiền* - Nguyễn Trọng Quản); Anh Ó sheltering and

helping Nguyệt Ba and her mother without concern for his own life (*Hà Hương phong nguyệt* - Lê Hoàng Mưu); Trần Trọng Nghĩa rescuing Chăng Cà Mum from Thạch Biền and Thạch Quýt (*Nghĩa hiệp kỳ duyên* - Nguyễn Chánh Sắt, 1920); ông Bạch Khiếu Nhân helping Chí Đại find work, arranging marriage with his granddaughter, and providing him with capital (*Ai làm được* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1922); Ba Thời sheltering and raising Được (*Cay đắng mùi đời* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1923); Lư Bích Ton helping Hồng Hoa with business strategies (*Đầu tóc mươn* - Lê Hoàng Mưu, 1924); Duy Linh helping Phi Phụng in times of hardship (*Nhơn tình ấm lạnh* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1926); neighbors supporting and helping the siblings Thăng Tý and con Quyên when their mother dies and their father disappears (*Cha con nghĩa nặng* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1929); Cao Sĩ Quý saving the life of Liên Tử Tâm, and in return, Liên Tử Tâm and her father help Cao Sĩ Quý's family overcome financial hardship (*Cố Ba Trành* - Nguyễn Ý Bửu, 1927); helping those less fortunate, such as Trinh helping her friend, Phụng helping Tâm's family (*Người thất chí* - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1938)...

Second, fine customs in family life. Scenes of family members gathering together during festivals and holidays, where those who are far away try to return home to visit their families and relatives. The lifestyle of Southern Vietnamese people is simple and rustic, just like the people themselves. A meal of a poor family is nonetheless warm and happy, such as the scene of Kim Sa's family sitting together around a meal consisting only of a bowl of fish sauce mixed with a fertilized duck egg, and the children competing for food, "clashing chopsticks above their heads making crunching sounds" (Nguyễn Bửu Mộc, *Mạng nhà nghèo*); then the scene where the children and the dog eat first, followed by the husband and father in *Chén cơm lạt của người thất nghiệp* (Sơn Vương, 1931)...

This shows a clear difference between the dining culture of Northern and Southern Vietnamese people. In *Trẻ con không biết ăn thịt chó* (Nam Cao), we see the opposite: regardless of wealth, when there are guests, meals are divided into two trays—an upper tray (for the husband, adult sons, elders, and guests), where the best dishes are placed; and a lower tray (for women, daughters, and younger children), containing the remaining food. Hierarchy is clearly reflected even in meals in Northern culture, following the principle of "ăn trông nời ngồi trông hướng." However, among Southern people, this custom has given way to a more egalitarian practice, where everyone has equal rights, at least in the meal.

Third, the inspiration of affirming traditional ethics and morality aims to educate people's lifestyle, moral conduct, and character. This may include: affection and ways of conduct between husband and wife, between parents and children, and among neighbors; the duties and responsibilities of officials toward the people; the roles and responsibilities of intellectuals in "enlightening the people's knowledge, strengthening the people's spirit, and improving the people's livelihood" toward society and the nation; and the responsibilities of youth in asserting themselves (through education, through business competition with foreigners, here including Hoa Kiêu, Indians, and the French)...

All these elements contribute to forming a literary current that conveys moral and ethical values in Southern Vietnam in the early twentieth century, with Hồ Biểu Chánh as a representative writer. Nguyễn Đình Chiểu once summarized this spirit of struggle for the people in the verse: "Chở bao nhiêu đạo thuyền không khẳm / Đâm mấy thằng gian bút chẳng tà." In addition, novels of this period also criticize the opportunistic way of living ("đục nước béo cò") of a segment of society, as they resort to any means to pursue fame and profit, even committing murder, betraying spouses, or showing ingratitude toward those who helped them, in order to seize what does not belong to them.

Conclusion

From the examination of the inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs and the inspiration of affirming fine traditional values in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century, it can be seen that these are not only two parallel modes of inspiration but also have a complementary and closely interactive relationship in constructing the cultural and social value system of the time. In a transitional

context marked by profound changes, Southern Vietnamese writers demonstrated an attitude that both criticized outdated elements that hinder human development and actively selected, preserved, and promoted positive traditional values.

The inspiration of criticizing obsolete customs enables literature to perform its function of social critique, exposing inadequacies in moral life and customs, thereby promoting the need for change and reform. Meanwhile, the inspiration of affirming fine traditional values plays a guiding role, reinforcing belief in the enduring values of the community and contributing to maintaining the stability and continuity of national culture. The interweaving of these two forms of inspiration shows that literature not only reflects reality but also actively participates in the process of adjusting and restructuring the social value system in a particular historical period.

From this, it can be further argued that the study of literary inspirations not only helps identify the characteristics of a specific literary period but also contributes to explaining deeper transformations in cultural and social consciousness. In the contemporary context, when many traditional values continue to face challenges from modern life, revisiting the manifestations of critical and affirmative inspirations in past literature may suggest new approaches to preserving, promoting, and redefining national cultural values.

References

- Bình Trọng. (1931). *Burning the Almanac* [Đốt lịch]. *Công luận báo*, (2000), February 14, 1931.
- Cao Thị Ngọc Hà. (1996). *Vietnamese Customary Novels – Development and Characteristics* [Tiểu thuyết phong tục Việt Nam - tiến trình và đặc điểm]. Ho Chi Minh City: Giáo dục Việt Nam.
- Hồ Biểu Chánh. (n.d.). *Hồ Biểu Chánh website*. Retrieved from <http://www.hobieuchanh.com/>
- Hồ Biểu Chánh. (1922b). *Chúa tàu Kim Quy*. hobieuchanh.com
- Hủ tục [evil customs] (n.d.). tratu.soha.vn
- Lê Hoàng Mưu. (2018a). *Hà Hương phong Nguyệt*. Võ Văn Nhơn (Ed.). Ho Chi Minh City Culture and Arts Publishing House
- Nguyễn Chánh Sắt. (2002). *Nghĩa hiệp kì duyên*. Literature Publishing House, Ho Chi Minh City
- Nguyễn Chánh Sắt. (2015). *Việt Nam Lê Thái Tổ*. (Reprinted from the 1929 edition). Hanoi: Hồng Đức.
- Nguyễn Kim Thản, Hồ Hải Thụy, & Nguyễn Đức Dương. (2005). Vietnamese dictionary [Từ điển tiếng Việt]. Saigon Culture Publishing House
- Phú Đức. (1999). *Châu về hiệp phố*. In Cao Xuân Mỹ (Ed.), *Văn xuôi Nam Bộ nửa đầu thế kỷ XX* [Southern Vietnamese prose in the first half of the twentieth century] (Vol. 1, pp. 250–394). Literature Publishing House, Ho Chi Minh City; Center for National Studies.
- Phú Đức. (1928). *Lửa lòng* (following *Châu về hiệp phố*, vol. 30)]. Saigon: Xưa Nay Printing House.
- Phú Đức. (1989). *Ngọc Lam Điền*. Tien Giang General Publishing House.

